

maximum yield gain obtained during the WS derived from the performance of hybrids vs Jaya was 544 kg ha⁻¹ in 1991 and 1,522 kg ha⁻¹ in 1995. Similarly, in DS, the yield gain in hybrid rice was 846 kg ha⁻¹ in 1991-92 and 1,634 kg ha⁻¹ in 1993-94. The heterosis for grain yield increased—from 14% (1991) to 31% (1995) in the WS, and from 8% (1991-92) to 27% (1993-94) in the DS. The results indicate that hybrids undoubtedly have a yield advantage over high-yielding varieties such as Jaya. The margin of yield gain increased over the years. The diversity of material added over time may be the reason for such gains. The hybrids are also as widely adaptable as Jaya. ■

Yield stability in rice hybrids

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Hybrid rice technology is considered to have the most potential and be readily exploitable to further raise the yield ceiling in the irrigated ecosystem. But successful exploitation over a large area depends on identifying stable hybrids. Yield heterosis is reported to be a variable trait, which depends not only on parent combinations but also on environmental conditions. Stability for yield of rice hybrids is therefore analyzed. We examined the stability of hybrids for yield in two sets of environments categorized as low and high. Grain yield data of 10 trials conducted between the 1994 wet season (WS) and 1995 WS were used. Locations with a mean yield lower than the grand mean yield were termed low environments, whereas those with a mean yield higher than the grand mean yield were identified as high environments. We analyzed grain yield data on eight hybrids in the 1994-95 WS and dry season tested along with inbred Jaya, Rasi, and IR36 at five locations. The mean yield and coefficient of variation over

seasons and locations were calculated for both hybrids and inbreds to find environment-dependent heterosis.

The mean grain yield advantage of the best-yielding hybrid over Jaya was calculated for each environment. The results indicated that the stability of rice hybrids for grain yield is comparable with that of the best inbred check variety, Jaya. Some of the hybrids, such as IR58025A / IR34686 and IR58025A / IR29723, showed better yield stability over seasons compared with Jaya. But the yield heterosis of the hybrids was better expressed in environments categorized as high. ■

Exploiting heterosis using TGMS lines in intra- and intersubspecific hybridization

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The performance of various thermo-sensitive genic male sterile (TGMS) lines was assessed in order to use them in two-line intra- and intersubspecific hybridization with wide compatibility lines. Some 26 lines comprising TGMS lines, indica accessions, and japonica with wide compatibility (WC) gene(s) were used to make 65 hybrids: 31 were indica / indica and 34 were indica / japonica (WC). Standard heterosis was recorded up to 58%. Seed yield (g plant⁻¹) ranged from 2.3 to 31.3. The number of heterotic combinations was higher in intersubspecific cross combinations. Spikelet fertility ranged from 2.7 to 88.4% in intersubspecific crosses and from 3.6 to 96.0% in intrasubspecific crosses. The WC lines were not universally compatible in all combinations. The TGMS line ID / 24 was completely

compatible with all WC as well as with other indica accessions.

A molecular phylogenetic map was constructed involving all 26 lines based on the polymorphism generated by 10 random primers—OPD3, OPU7, OPU14, OPZ18, OPZ19, OPZ20, OPA7 + OPA6, and OPA12 + OPD5. By using the un-weighted pair-group method, arithmetic average (UPGMA), a dendrogram was made, taking into consideration the distance calculated based on Jaccard similarity indices. The genetic distances were from 0.2 to 0.88. The height in hybrids increased as the genetic distance between the parents widened. With genetic distance > 0.70 among parents, spikelet fertility and grain yield plant⁻¹ decreased considerably. Heterotic combinations were observed when the genetic distance ranged from 0.4 to 0.7 among parents. ■

Developing CMS and restorer lines of tropical rice hybrids

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The successful development and cultivation of hybrid rice in China in 1976 encouraged IRRI scientists and collaborating countries to intensify this research in 1980. Because the Chinese hybrids and parental lines were not adapted to the tropics, IRRI began collaborating with several tropical rice-growing countries to develop suitable parental lines and hybrids. By 1989, IRRI developed two commercially usable cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines that, when combined with easily available restorers among elite tropical indica rice cultivars, produced hundreds of experimental rice hybrids. Some of these yielded about 1 t ha⁻¹ more than inbred checks in national trials under irrigated conditions. By 1994, India, Vietnam, and the Philippines had released some promising rice hybrids for commercial cultivation by farmers. New and better CMS lines are now available in the genetic background of irrigated, rainfed, boro, and

aromatic rice cultivars. The cytoplasmic base has been diversified to protect future rice hybrids from outbreaks of disease or insect pests. Breeding indica / tropical japonica hybrids has begun with the development of CMS lines in the background of tropical japonica. ■

Developing Pusa 3A, a Basmati CMS line

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Basmati rice occupies a significant place in India's rice economy on account of its high export potential. With the release of Pusa Basmati 1, the first high-yielding semidwarf Basmati variety meeting quality standards, India leaped ahead in Basmati rice production. Further improvement in Basmati yield may be possible with the adoption of hybrid rice technology.

Various Basmati rice lines were testcrossed with IR58025A. Pusa Basmati 1 showed complete sterility and proved to be a perfect maintainer of wild abortive (WA) cyto sterility. The pollen sterility in the F_1 hybrid was 100%. The F_1 was backcrossed to Pusa Basmati 1 and a BC_1 population of about 600 plants was raised. All the plants showed 100% pollen sterility. Segregation was observed for various plant characters. Twenty BC_1 plants that were closer to Pusa Basmati 1 for various characters were backcrossed to Pusa Basmati 1. About 30 seedlings in each of the 20 BC_2 progenies showed 100% pollen sterility. Cooking quality of the 20 pollen donors was analyzed. The best five donors showing good cooking quality were selected on the basis of their similarity to Pusa Basmati 1 for various agronomic characters such as plant height, panicle length, spikelet morphology, and days to 50% flowering. These plants were again backcrossed to the selected five pollen donors, thus maintaining the identity

of the pollen donors for the respective population. The BC_3 plants raised from the above crosses were screened for pollen sterility; all the plants were 100% sterile. Three plants were selected from each BC_3 progeny row and these were again backcrossed to their respective pollen parent from Pusa Basmati 1. Progenies from pollen plants No. 1 and 3 (Pusa Basmati 1-1 and Pusa Basmati 1-3) had all the morphological characters of Pusa Basmati 1. They were further backcrossed to their respective pollen plants—Pusa Basmati 1-1 and Pusa Basmati 1-3, both with excellent cooking quality traits. The CMS line derived from Pusa Basmati 1-3 has been named Pusa 3A. This line shows stable sterility under different environmental conditions at New Delhi and Aduthurai, Tamil Nadu, during the two different rice seasons. This line is now being used extensively for test-crossing with both Basmati and non-Basmati male parents. A few promising combinations with Basmati restorers have been identified. It was also found that heterosis with non-Basmati restorers was far greater than with Basmati restorers for various characters, including yield. ■

Screening rice genotypes for thermosensitive genic male sterility reaction

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Two-line rice hybrids were found to be more heterotic than three-line hybrids. Constraints of the three-line system can also be avoided in the two-line system. Any rice variety can be used as a pollen parent in the two-line system irrespective of the presence of a restorer gene. The two-line system also offers the advantage of easy seed production. For photoperiod-sensitive genic male sterility (PGMS) vs thermosensitive genic male sterility (TGMS), the TGMS system is more useful for the weather

conditions that prevail in southern India. We therefore screened some diverse genotypes to identify potential lines. Staggered sowings and plantings were done during the 1995-96 wet and dry seasons. We carried out pollen studies on these lines and also recorded spikelet fertility. Data on pollen sterility were correlated with minimum, maximum, and daily mean temperatures during the critical period of sensitivity of the lines, that is, 10 d from the third day after panicle initiation.

During the 1995 wet season, one TGMS line—IR68949-5-31-34—exhibited complete pollen and spikelet sterility for a period of 51 consecutive d. The mean daily temperatures during this 51-d period were between 27.1 and 28.4 °C. The same line transformed to partial fertility when the average temperatures reached 26 °C and below.

During the 1996 dry season, a second TGMS line, IR68945-33-4-14-40, was found to be completely sterile for a period of 15 d. The mean daily temperature regimes at the critical period of sensitivity ranged from 23.5 to 26.5 °C. Later, this line transformed to partial or complete fertility. The two TGMS lines identified in this study may be used to develop new two-line rice hybrids for enhancing heterosis and thus production and productivity of the rice crop. ■

Identifying parental lines in hybrid rice by RAPD fingerprinting

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The commercial production of hybrid rice hinges on three-line breeding, male sterile, maintainer, and restorer lines. Developing and producing new parental lines are essential for the sustainability of hybrid rice. Characterizing these lines based on morphological and phenological characters consumes time, lacks sufficient resolving power, and is influenced by